

Synthesis and Characterisation of Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) Complexes with Schiff Base of 5-Phenylazosalicylideneaniline

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A new Schiff base ligand is synthesised by condensation of 5-phenylazosalicylaldehyde with aniline (PASA). The complexes of the type $M(\text{PASA})\text{Cl}$ [$M = \text{Co(II)}$, Ni(II) and Cu(II)] and Fe(PASA)Cl , have been prepared in the solid state and characterised by their elemental analysis, molar conductance, magnetic moments at room temperature and infrared spectral studies. The complexes are paramagnetic having subnormal magnetic moments, they may have MNON Cl chromophores instead of the expected MN_2O group. The complexes are thought to possess either dimeric or linear polymeric structures.

THERE have been a number of studies of metal complexes of Schiff base ligands formed from salicylaldehyde or substituted salicylaldehydes with various aromatic amines¹⁻⁶. But it is noted that, the Schiff base formed by condensation of 5-phenylazosalicylaldehyde with aniline did not receive attention in the field of structural chemistry, although few authors have first reported the metal complexes of 5-phenylazosalicylaldehyde^{7,8}. It is therefore, thought by the present authors, that 5-phenylazosalicylidene aniline Schiff base would be an ideal ligand for synthesising it and for preparation of the metal complexes. In view of this, we present here the results of magnetic and infrared spectroscopic investigations of some new Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) metal complexes of Schiff base ligand 5-phenylazosalicylidene aniline (I).

Experimental

Materials: The chemicals used in this investigation were of reagent grade. Salicylaldehyde and aniline were distilled before use.

Ligand: 5-Phenylazosalicylaldehyde (PAS) was prepared according to the method of Das and Trivedi⁹. Then the Schiff base was prepared by refluxing aniline with PAS in 1:1 molar ratio in alcoholic medium on water bath. The Schiff base 5-phenylazosalicylidene aniline (PASA) thus separated after cooling was then filtered and crystallised from alcohol (M. P. 140°).

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Complexes: The metal complexes were prepared by treating the Schiff base dissolved in the least amount of ethanol with metal salts (FeCl_3 , $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) in molar ratio 1:1. The reaction mixture was refluxed for about 1 hr. The solution was then reduced to smaller volume on a water bath and after cooling pH was raised to 8 by 1:1 ammonia in alcohol. The respective solid complexes were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in a desiccator over fused CaCl_2 . The complexes were purified by soxhlet extraction.

Chemical Analysis: The solid ligand (PASA) obtained was analysed for carbon and hydrogen. The complexes were analysed for their metal and halogen by standard methods. The result of chemical analysis are recorded in Table 1.

Physical Measurements: The molar conductance of the complexes were made using ELICO (M-8) conductivity bridge with a cell having cell constant 0.829 cm^{-1} , manufactured by Electronic and Industrial Instrument Company, Hyderabad. The solutions were prepared in DMF and diluted to the required strength (10^{-3} M). The magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on a gouy balance at room temperature using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as calibrant. The i.r. spectra of the ligand and the complexes in nujol mull and KBr disc methods were recorded on Perkin Elmer 457 and 221 spectrometers in the $200\text{-}4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region.

Results and Discussion

The reaction of Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) chlorides with Schiff base (PASA) gave only 1:1 complexes $M(\text{PASA})\text{Cl}$ [$M = \text{Co(II)}$, Ni(II) and Cu(II)]

TABLE 1 - COLOR, M.P., CONDUCTIVITY, MAGNETIC MOMENTS AND ANALYTICAL DATA FOR Co(II), Ni(II) Cu(II) AND Fe(II) SCHIFF BASE COMPLEXES

Complex	M.P. °C. (Melts & decomposes)	Colour of the complexes	Metal %		Chlorine %		Conductivity ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
			Found	Cal.	Found	Cal.		
Co(PASA)Cl	210	Light red	14.87	14.88	8.40	8.90	5.760	3.6
Ni(PASA)Cl	230	Yellowish green	14.55	14.86	8.50	8.96	2.173	2.9
Cu(PASA)Cl	290	Yellowish green	15.20	14.91	9.10	8.89	2.413	1.8
Fe(PASA)Cl ₂	210	Darkish red	13.40	13.07	16.40	16.63	20.850	5.1
Ligand (PASA) C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₃ O	140	Red	Found : C=75.5%, H=4.84%		Required : C=75.74%, H=4.94%			

and Fe(PASA)Cl₂. The complexes can not be recrystallised from ethanol, because they were found to undergo thermal decomposition, when an attempt was made to recrystallise from hot solutions on account of low solubilities.

All the products are yellowish green to darkish red solids and are stable against light and atmosphere. They are soluble in polar solvents such as dimethyl formamide (DMF), pyridine etc. Practically all are insoluble in common organic solvents such as ethanol, acetone and benzene.

The molar conductance of these complexes in DMF at the concentration 10⁻³ M fall in the range 2—6 ohm⁻¹ cm² mole⁻¹. This value is too small to account for any dissociation of the complexes in DMF. Hence, these can be regarded as non-electrolytes in that solvent¹⁰. In case of Fe(III) complex, the value

is 21 ohm⁻¹ cm² mole⁻¹ and this may be due to the partial displacement of the chloro group by DMF in the coordination sphere of the complex.

The magnetic moments of the complexes calculated from the corrected magnetic susceptibilities determined at room temperature are given in Table 1. The magnetic moments μ_{eff} values reported for the complexes are lower than the spin-only value of respective metal ion complex¹¹. The subnormal magnetic moments observed in the case of Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) Schiff base complexes are accounted for by assuming dimeric or chain polymeric structures in the solid state and considerable interaction between metal ion systems owing to the spin-spin coupling, occurring antiferromagnetic interaction mechanism operating through the orbitals of metal ions¹¹⁻¹⁸. These results may be accounted for by assuming predominantly dimeric or polymeric structures for these complexes.

TABLE 2 - SELECTED INFRARED ABSORPTION FREQUENCIES (cm⁻¹) OF PASA SCHIFF BASE LIGAND AND THEIR METAL COMPLEXES

Ligand	Fe(PASA)Cl ₂	Co(PASA)Cl	Ni(PASA)Cl	Cu(PASA)Cl	Assignment
2700 - 2800brw	—	—	—	—	Intramolecular H bonded OH stretching
1625s	1620s	1610s	1615s	1615s	ν C=N stretching
1590s 1580s 1570s	1525m	1535m	1530m	1525m	ν N=N + ν C=C aromatic stretching
1458vs	1385vs	1400vs	1406vs	1403vs	
1280s	1325brm	1322s	1330s	1345vs	Phenolic ν C-O stretching
—	465brm	480brm	470m 482m	460m 470m	ν M-N
—	370brm	365m 375m	365m 370m	350m 370w	ν M-O

The selected infrared frequencies along with their tentative assignments are listed in Table 2. The broad and weak band with a fine structure in the region 2700-2800 cm^{-1} appearing in the spectra of the free ligand is attributed to the intramolecular hydrogen bonded OH established between the aldehydic *o*-OH group and the basic nitrogen atom. This assignment is in line with that made by other investigators¹⁴⁻¹⁶. The broad band of ligand disappears in the complexes leaving only a fine structure, which is due mainly to the CH modes.

In the PASA Schiff base, one can expect also stretching frequencies due to $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$, $\nu\text{C}=\text{C}$ and $\nu\text{N}=\text{N}$. Eventhough it has been reported that 5-phenylazosalicylaldehyde would show $\text{N}=\text{N}$ stretching frequency around 1500-1575 cm^{-1} and 1460-1490 cm^{-1} . It is however, difficult to assign the $\text{N}=\text{N}$ stretching to the specific band in the aromatic azo compounds, because there is extensive coupling between $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$, $\nu\text{C}=\text{C}$ and $\nu\text{N}=\text{N}$ modes. It is still more cumbersome in the Schiff base 5-phenylazosalicylidene aniline. Therefore the bands in the region 1460-1590 cm^{-1} are tentatively assigned to coupled $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C}) + \nu(\text{N}=\text{N})$ and these bands have remarkable change in their stretching frequencies on going from ligand to metal complex (Table 2).

In the ligand spectrum the strong band appearing at 1625 cm^{-1} is assigned to $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ stretching mode. In the metal complexes this band shifts to lower frequency region indicating that the coordination bond is formed between nitrogen of azomethine group and metal ion. This is in good agreement with previous assignment^{6,16,20} for the $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ mode in Schiff base complexes.

The strong band found around 1280 cm^{-1} in the ligand PASA Schiff base is assigned to the phenolic C-O stretching vibration¹⁸. This is shifted towards higher frequency on complexation. The higher frequency shift observed of the phenolic C-O bond in going from a hydrogen bonded structure to a covalent metal bonded structure, may be due to higher mesomeric interaction in the complex, which is activated by the presence of the metal ion¹⁷.

The metal-ligand, metal-oxygen, metal-nitrogen and metal-chloride vibrational modes are generally found to occur between 200-600 cm^{-1} . However, in these complexes, it is not easy to assign $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ vibrations, as the various skeletal vibrations of the ligand interfere with $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ vibrations. The assignments made are purely tentative and are based mainly on the information available in the literature.

Eventhough Nakamoto¹⁸ reported that, no band in the structure of Schiff base complexes can be assigned to the $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ vibration, because of strong coupling between various modes. There are many other authors^{19,20} who have assigned metal-nitrogen bands in the region 400-600 cm^{-1} . The medium and some-

what broad intense band found in the region 460-480 cm^{-1} (Table-2) attributed to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ vibration. Taking into consideration of the observations of other authors^{21,22} towards $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ assignment, medium intensity bands appearing in the region 350-370 cm^{-1} for these metal complexes are assigned to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ vibration. Thus we have assigned $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ stretching modes to higher frequencies than $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ modes, as previous assignments on metal complexes containing "NO" ligands^{23,24}.

With the help of analytical data, conductivity, magnetic and infrared spectral data, it may be suggested that, all the metal ions have coordination number four in these complexes, except in Fe(III), where it is five. The construction of the models for the complexes indicates that, the monomeric structure involves much steric hindrance as the ligand molecule has to attach itself to one and the same metal ion through all its coordinating sites. The insolubility of the complexes in common solvents makes one to suggest a dimeric (II) or an extended polymeric structure (III). In view of these observations, we propose following structures for the complexes in which metal ions are maintained at the same coordination number.

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